

BUSINESS MODEL TRANSFORMATIONS IN B2B DIGITAL MULTIMODAL LOGISTICS PLATFORM ECOSYSTEM: INSIGHTS FROM MARKETPLACE OWNERS, SELLERS AND BUYERS

ABSTRACT Full Paper

Digitalization and sustainability imperatives are transforming the logistics industry; however, the evolution of business models (BMs) in emerging business-to-business (B2B) digital multimodal marketplaces has not been thoroughly explored. This study investigates how one of the first B2B digital multimodal marketplace ecosystems—designed to calculate emissions and promote more sustainable logistics services—affects the BMs of three key actor groups: marketplace owners, sellers and buyers.

We used a qualitative research design based on the Business Model Canvas (BMC). To gather data, we analyzed the current (AS-IS) and future (TO-BE) BMs. Additionally, we created detailed questionnaires structured around the BMC framework, which were completed by representatives from each actors group.

A hybrid deductive-inductive coding approach allowed us to integrate the established BMC framework with emergent themes. Our analysis reveals significant transformations in the key activities, followed by changes in key resources, channels and revenue streams. In contrast, we observed comparatively fewer changes in the areas of value propositions and customer segments. We identified several common patterns and group-specific differences that will guide the development of distinct BMs for each actor group.

These insights deepen the theoretical understanding of how digital logistics marketplaces drive BM transformation, while also highlighting the challenges, risks, and necessary adjustments managers in logistics industry should address when integrating a digital marketplace ecosystem.

This study is one of the first to analyze changes in the business models of companies adopting a B2B digital logistics platform ecosystem. Additionally, it is the first to explore a multimodal and environmentally conscious platform ecosystem.

Keywords: business-to-business, digital marketplace, logistics, business models, transformation

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, advancements in digital technology have revolutionized the way companies conduct business, interact with customers and compete. Many businesses now operate entirely online, while companies such as Uber, Airbnb, Facebook and others, have achieved remarkable success in selling products and services through business-to-consumer (B2C) and consumers-to-consumer (C2C) models by utilizing digital platforms or marketplaces. They become an alternative to compete in this rapidly changing digital landscape (Berman et al., 2022, Martín-Peña et al., 2024, Xie et al., 2022).

However, while much attention has been given to B2C and C2C platforms, industrial digital platforms that focus on business-to-business (B2B) interactions have also become a significant part of today's digital ecosystem. As noted in several studies (Verfürth and Helwing-Hentschel, 2024, Eerikäinen, Bagnato and Giordino, 2024), B2B platforms are an essential component of the modern economy. In the eyes of both academic researchers and practitioners, industrial digital platform ecosystems represent key developments in pursuing a fully achieved digital transformation as they collect and share data across the ecosystem and commercialize innovations across many partners within the ecosystem (Riemensperger and Falk, 2020, Pauli, 2021, Jovanovic et al., 2022). They also offer benefits in low-cost inter-organization information connectivity, real-time visibility, and adaptable partnership configurations (Rios Lam, 2018).

A unified classification of B2B industrial digital platforms does not exist, as various authors have employed different classification approaches. We have decided to take into account the most recent, classification by Madanaguli et al. (2023) and Jovanovic et al. (2022) who claim that the classification of industrial digital platforms and the BMs they adopt depends on the extent of data integration with the platform and the extent of ecosystem integration. The extent of data integration is the extent to which quality data are integrated to create, deliver and capture value. On the other hand, the extent of ecosystem integration is the extent to which BMs of different ecosystem partners are integrated into digital platform. They highlighted 3 different types of industrial digital platforms: (1) the product service platform, (2) the industrial transaction platform and (3) industrial digital platform ecosystem. This paper examines the industrial digital platform ecosystems.

A digital or e-platform ecosystem is a virtual platform that connects multiple sellers and buyers, facilitating the exchange of goods, services, and information (Pidun et al., 2022, Hein et al., 2020, Martín-Peña et al., 2024, Cano et al., 2023). This ecosystem includes a platform owner who implements and maintains governance mechanisms and value creation strategies, as well as complementors that offer various services and solutions such as financing, insurance, customs brokerage, information technology (IT) and analytics tools etc. (Hein et al., 2020, Martín-Peña et al., 2024, Mishra and Tripathi, 2020). Within industrial digital ecosystems there are two primary value creation mechanisms: transaction mechanisms and innovation capabilities. The transaction mechanism enables sellers and buyers to exchange value in a mutually beneficial manner, while the innovation capabilities mechanism relates to the integration of complementary offerings that enhance the overall value of the platform's ecosystem (Hein et al., 2020).

The growing significance of digital platforms has prompted increased research focus. Initially, studies concentrated on B2C markets (Repenning and Hardaker, 2024, Chu et al., 2023), while research on B2B platforms started to develop but has so far received less attention (Verfürth and Helwing-Hentschel, 2024, Dolata, 2024). Although there is a broad consensus among

researchers that digital platforms have emerged as engines of BM innovation for companies using them to sell or buy services—offering fresh value streams beyond traditional sales channels and revenue models (Martín-Peña et al., 2024, Madanaguli et al., 2023, Veile et al., 2022)—the understanding of how digital B2B platforms ecosystems are transforming the BMs of participating organizations, both in logistics and other sectors, remains limited (Madanaguli et al., 2023). Consequently, very few owners of B2B platforms have been able to successfully establish viable BMs for their offerings, largely due to numerous deficiencies. Moreover, future research is needed on the role of sustainability in platform-based BMs (Kohtamäki et al., 2019).

As Pidun et al. (2022) observed, many platform providers struggle to fully capitalize on the value and opportunities presented by digital marketplaces. This challenge arises primarily from the high complexity of industrial digital platform ecosystems and the rapid pace of technological development (Foss and Saebi, 2017, Troise et al., 2022). Managing such marketplaces effectively is not straightforward, as platform providers must ensure their BM components are aligned with those of all the other partners within the ecosystem. Unlike B2C platforms, industrial digital platforms often have a more specialized (or narrowly targeted) set of customers and complementors. Consequently, platform owners must carefully manage their platforms to maximize value for all participants in the ecosystem—including themselves, sellers, and buyers.

According to Xie et al. (2022), although various aspects of how companies use digital platforms have been studied, the capability configuration and BM innovation within digital platform contexts remain largely unexplored. It has not yet been discovered how enterprises are promoting BM innovation through their adoption of digital platforms. Previous research also indicates that findings related to BMs in industrial digital marketplaces cannot be directly applied without careful consideration, due to the diversity of platforms in terms of market types (B2B, B2C), industry variations, and digital marketplace patterns (Repenning and Hardaker, 2024, Veile et al., 2022). Additionally, developing new BMs within digital platforms often requires careful consideration of scalability and flexibility. Future research examining different case studies may yield valuable insights and contribute to the development of innovative frameworks and best practices for creating and managing new BMs in digital marketplace settings (Eerikäinen, 2020).

Given the complexity of digital marketplaces, it is essential to develop a robust and well-suited BM, as available generic models rarely deliver the desired value to platform providers. Recognizing that little research exists on BM transformations in digital logistics marketplaces, this study aims to investigate the nature of these transformations—specifically the exact changes in value creation, capture, and delivery. It focuses on both the platform owner of a B2B digital marketplace ecosystem and the ecosystem partners (sellers/buyers of services, IT and other tool developers, and data providers) adopting a digital marketplace ecosystem.

In this article, we investigate the case company—an operator of the first multimodal logistics digital marketplace ecosystem developed within the Advanced Multimodal Marketplace for Low-Emission and Energy-Efficient Transportation (ADMIRAL) project (see Section 4). The developed ecosystem will facilitate interaction and data exchange among various supply and logistics chain partners, including port authorities, shipping lines, cargo owners, and logistics service providers. By digitizing workflows, the platform will streamline traditionally paper-intensive processes and offer real-time visibility and analytics throughout the supply chain. It will also utilize artificial intelligence (AI) to provide tools and insights for optimizing port calls, vessel scheduling, route planning, and various logistics processes, aiming to reduce inefficiencies and improve turnaround times (awake.ai, 2025). A key promise of this marketplace ecosystem is the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and other resource costs

through the identification of more efficient schedules, routes, and usage patterns (awake.ai, 2025).

The following research questions (RQ) are addressed:

RQ1. Which type(s) of BM transformations—innovation, evolution, or adaptation—are required to transform a traditional freight digital platform into a platform ecosystem that also reduces environmental emissions?

RQ2. Which type(s) of BM transformations—innovation, evolution, or adaptation—are required for sellers and buyers to effectively use a freight digital ecosystem?

RQ3. What changes in the creation, delivery, and capture of value to the BMs are necessary for marketplace owners, sellers and buyers to effectively manage or use a freight digital platform ecosystem?

RQ4. What key risks and challenges do platform owners and their partners face in building and operating a digital freight marketplace ecosystem?

Given the inquiry-based nature of this research, we opted for an inductive, multiple-case study (6x) approach instead of a statistical one. This design was chosen to allow for a deeper exploration of BM transformations—an aspect that is often challenging to capture through quantitative methods alone. Specifically, we examined changes in BMs within a digital logistics marketplace ecosystem by analyzing the models of key stakeholder groups: one platform owner and five sellers and buyers of logistics services- logistics service providers (three parcel carriers, one transport provider, one freight forwarder and one port services provider).

To guide our analysis, we utilized the BMC developed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010). Data collection involved a comparison analysis of AS-IS BMC (current BMs) and TO-BE (future BMs) BMC of all ecosystem partners, supplemented by ten detailed questionnaires with representatives from each stakeholder group. This approach enabled us to capture the changes, adaptations, and innovations in value creation, capture, and delivery that arise within the ecosystem.

This study addresses both a theoretical research gap and an organizational practical problem. *Theoretical contribution:* This study seeks to fill a gap in the existing literature by expanding theoretical knowledge about BM transformations that occur through the management and use of environmentally sustainable, digital platform ecosystems but also by providing novel insights that have not been explored in previous research.

Practical contribution: This paper emphasizes the significant changes in BMs, opportunities, and risks for digital platform owners and their partners. The insights provided empower them to make more informed decisions regarding sustainable operations and the development of new revenue streams. Additionally, IT and other tools providers can pinpoint complementary services that align with the evolving needs of logistics platforms.

The paper is organized as follows: It begins with an introduction, followed by a literature review section. Chapter three outlines the methodological approach, which is followed by the presentation of the case study on the industrial digital marketplace. Next, the results from the questionnaires are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a summary that includes limitations and suggestions for future research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEWS

Three literature reviews inform our research: BM transformations, industrial B2B digital platform ecosystems and their role in transforming the BMs of ecosystem partners.

2.1. Understanding BM transformation

A BM outlines how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value. It describes the key components, often referred to as “building blocks”, which include the product or service offering, target audience, revenue streams, and internal operations (activities and resources). Additionally, it explains how these elements work together to generate value for both the customer and the organization (Saebi et al., 2017, Demil and Lecocq, 2010, Doz and Kosonen, 2010, Dunford et al., 2010, McGrath, 2010, Teece, 2010).

The initial design of a company's BM is influenced by a variety of external and internal factors. However, internal and external factors—such as the need to improve competitive positioning, respond to significant changes in the environment, or other considerations—often force companies to transform their BMs (George and Bock, 2011, Savič et al., 2016). BM transformation represents a change in the logic according to which value is created, delivered, and captured (Frishammar and Parida, 2019). A successful BM transformation can, and often does, involve change in several dimensions.

There are three primary options for BM transformation: (1) BM evolution, (2) BM adaptation and (3) BM innovation. The simplest alteration is the evolution of the BM, which mostly involves standardizations, replications, and primarily maintenance of the existing BM. BM adaptation involves changes that management makes to the existing BM in response to external factors such as shifts in the competitive environment, advancements in information and communication technologies, customer preferences, and supplier bargaining power (Saebi et al., 2017, Xie et al., 2022, Korneeva et al., 2023). In this case, management aligns the BM with changes or requirements in the external environment.

On the other hand, BM innovation requires management to actively conceptualize and implement new BMs that can respond to new conditions driven by either internal or external factors (Bucherer et al., 2012). This type of BM alteration necessitates changes in the overall configuration of the BM, the diversification with additional new BM that has been created, the acquisition of an additional, already existing, BMs or the transformation (of the entire BMs or a combination of its value proposition, value creation and deliver, and value capture elements) into another BM (Codini et al., 2023, Bucherer et al., 2012).

2.2. Understanding industrial B2B digital platform ecosystem BM

An industrial digital platform ecosystem usually consists of companies that buy services or products and those that provide them. The real value of the ecosystem comes from a range of complementary services offered by "complementors". Industrial B2B digital platform ecosystem BM, therefore, relies on the active and coordinated contributions of all partners within the ecosystem (Frishammar and Parida, 2019, Vänskä, 2020).

A comprehensive review and critical analysis of the existing literature on B2B industrial digital platforms BMs was conducted by Madanaguli et al. (2023). Given the depth, extent, and recency of their work, along with the overall scarcity of research on this topic, we rely on this source to present an understanding of industrial B2B digital platform ecosystem BMs rather

than conducting a separate literature review. Accordingly, the following discussion is entirely based on their work.

To enable complementors in a B2B digital platform ecosystem to *create value*, platform providers must ensure that their solutions are compatible. When all stakeholders are aligned, it fosters effective value creation and helps retain customers. To meet the evolving needs of customers, platform leaders must not only drive their own digital transformation but also support their partners in adapting to digital environments. This collaboration strengthens trust and encourages closer partnerships (Madanaguli et al., 2023).

The *value delivery* process in B2B is complex and interdependent, requiring strong digital transformation efforts. A robust digital infrastructure is essential for connecting partners, enabling real-time data sharing, and supporting efficient decision-making. Additionally, integrating technologies such as AI and machine learning (ML) fosters further advancements. To effectively create and deliver value, all partners need to adopt and understand the necessary digital technologies. The platform operator plays a crucial role in standardizing processes and providing ongoing support (Madanaguli et al., 2023).

Capture value: Because B2B platforms typically have fewer customers than B2C platforms, selecting the right revenue model for an industrial platform is especially important, as it can significantly influence the platform's success and profitability. Regardless of the actor type, the platform leader must ensure a fair distribution of value and a transparent allocation of revenues. Consequently, clarifying the flow of revenues as well as each actor's costs and benefits is critical to designing an effective revenue model. Beyond creating revenue models for value capture and fair distribution, platform leaders must also conduct risk assessment and management, especially regarding competition and complementors (Madanaguli et al., 2023).

The dimensions of value creation, value capture, and value delivery within a BM are deeply interconnected. For a business to succeed, it must effectively manage each of these dimensions and ensure their alignment. This requires examining the synergetic effects across these three dimensions, such as the relationships between value creation and capture, value creation and delivery, and value delivery and capture (Ritter and Lettl, 2018).

Despite existing research, there is still a limited understanding of how co-creation processes, which are integral to B2B platforms, actually unfold in practice (Hein et al., 2020, Tian et al., 2021, Parida et al., 2019).

2.3 The role of digital platforms ecosystems in transformation partners' business modes

So far, we have not identified any research examining the transformation of BMs in companies that partner with B2B digital platform ecosystems in the logistics sector, nor have we found studies on the broader influence of B2B digital platform ecosystems. The closest works to our research focus are those by Veile et al. (2022) and Ritter and Lettl (2018), which, while they do not directly address BM transformations, still provide a useful basis for comparing and contextualizing our findings.

According to Veile et al. (2022), the introduction of digital platforms triggers significant shifts in key partners, value propositions, and revenue streams. Notably, digitalization, data, knowledge, and software become major sources of value creation. Offering additional solutions from external providers (IT and other tools developers) results in heightened competition or co-competition, which can enhance customization and generate new forms of value for customers. The study also highlights buyer-supplier relationships and trust as critical factors in driving collaboration and reducing transaction costs. Additionally, co-competition emerges as a notable

trend, with companies increasingly including competitors and technology providers as partners—although they often remain cautious about sharing sensitive data.

In contrast, a study of Ruggieri et al. (2018) shows that while startups across various sectors frequently rely on proprietary platforms powered by specialized algorithms and maintain low fixed costs, their value propositions differ. Some prioritize entirely new solutions or network effects, others emphasize cost-effectiveness and custom-tailored services, and still others provide educational or entertainment platforms. Despite their varied offerings, these startups share a reliance on highly qualified teams for platform development and a focus on proprietary channels—customer care via email, phone, and chat-bots—and algorithmic improvements as their core activities.

Another relevant study on BM innovation in Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) collaborating with a digital platform is provided by Bagnato and Giordino (2024). The research shows that such partnerships challenge traditional approaches and foster new ideas, products, or services by offering SMEs access to external networks, resources, and expertise. This collaboration facilitates knowledge exchange, improves operational efficiency, and extends market reach beyond geographical boundaries, enabling SMEs to refine their BMs, reduce waste, and strengthen community ties—thus creating both economic and social value.

Moreover, incorporating digital strategies into SMEs' overall objectives enhances digital skills, data-driven decision-making, and alignment with emerging market trends. These partnerships also broaden market access, allowing SMEs to achieve economies of scale, develop new revenue streams, and bolster financial stability. By leveraging resources from digital marketplaces and collaborating on joint ventures, SMEs can streamline operations, lower costs, and continuously innovate—ultimately strengthening and sustaining their BMs (Bagnato and Giordino, 2024).

Research by Vänskä (2020) indicates that digital platform ecosystems offer SMEs lower coordination and operational costs, resource-sharing benefits, and new opportunities for value co-creation. However, realizing these advantages requires a shared vision, collaborative capabilities, and adaptable processes, while challenges such as data-sharing risks, underdeveloped alliance management skills, outdated systems, and power imbalances can hinder success.

According to Xie et al. (2022), digital platforms also help firms innovate existing BMs—often via capability reconfiguration—enabling rapid shifts in how they create and capture value. In a study of four SMEs, Korneeva et al. (2023) found that limited digitalization skills can facilitate basic BM evolution, but more advanced capabilities (e.g., agility, knowledge management, and networking) are crucial for substantial transformation.

Lastly, de Oliveira and Cortimiglia (2017) emphasize the importance of identifying each stakeholder's unique resources, continuously monitoring co-creation dynamics, and focusing on scalable revenue streams—especially for platforms reliant on user-generated data. Ensuring equitable value distribution among participants not only fosters sustainability but also strengthens the overall viability of the platform BM.

2.3. Identified research gap and contributions

Despite numerous studies examining digital platforms and their impact on BM transformation, there has been a lack of research focusing specifically on how B2B industrial platform ecosystems partners in the logistics sector adapt their BMs to include both digital platform ecosystem and environmentally conscious platform ecosystem. This gap is particularly

important because a “one-size-fits-all” approach fails to consider the unique operational complexities and stakeholder dynamics within the logistics industry.

To address this gap, our study investigates how B2B digital logistics platform ecosystem developed within ADMIRAL project, transforms BMs of platform provider, buyers and sellers. Through a comparative analysis of various ecosystem partners, we identify commonalities and differences in value creation, delivery, and capture. These findings not only enhance theoretical understanding of platform-driven BM transformations but also provide practical insights for the logistics sector and beyond, as they seek to reduce emissions and develop sustainable, digitally driven BMs.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design

There is a lack of insights concerning BMs transformation when using B2B digital marketplace ecosystems, suggesting the need for a theory-building approach. We therefore employ a qualitative case study method (Eloranta and Turunen, 2016), following two-step approach: (1) analysing the BM of several companies from three actor groups in B2B digital platform ecosystem, to identify expected modifications and any inter-group differences and similarities, and (2) using a questionnaire-based method to explore and understand in detail the dynamics of BM transformations within this context of B2B.

By investigating multiple partners rather than single company within one group of platform’s ecosystem partners, we capture diverse perspectives and variations, enabling us to compare and contrast different examples, identify common patterns and unique features (Baber et al., 2019, Huberman, 2014). This approach enhances the generalizability and offers stronger evidence compared to single-case study.

Our analysis applies the BMC, which covers three BM dimensions (value creation, value offering and value capture) divided into nine building blocks (key partners, key activities, key resources, value propositions, customer relationships, customer segments, key resources, channels, cost structure and revenue streams) (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). Although various methods for BM analysis exist (e.g. Value proposition, Interface, Service platform, Organizing model, Revenue (VISOR) model, Service, Technology, Organization, Finance (STOF) model, etc.) we chose BMC for its simplicity in understanding, interpretation, comparison, and data interrelation, as well as its proven effectiveness in prior research. Figure 3.1 presents the methodological approach:

Figure 3.1 Overview of the methodological approach

3.2. Data collection

Data collection involved comparing AS-IS (current) and TO-BE (envisioned) BMCs, supplemented with seven detailed questionnaires with representatives from various actor groups. This approach captures the changes, adaptations, and innovations in value creation, capture, and delivery within the digital marketplace ecosystem.

3.2.1. AS-IS vs. TO-BE BMCs

The AS-IS BM describes company’s current BM, while TO-BE BM reflects how the model might transform through the use, management, or development of digital marketplace ecosystem solutions. A comparative analysis of AS-IS and TO-BE BMCs was conducted based on completed BMCs from six case companies (Figure 3.2). One company, which offers two distinct services, submitted two separate BMCs: one for its Roll-On/Roll-Off (RO-RO) operations and another for its freight forwarding services. A more detailed explanation of the sample is available in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Types of companies that completed BMCs

3.2.2. Questionnaire protocol development

Given the logistical challenges of scheduling semi-structured interviews with representatives from various departments of selected case companies, we opted to distribute the questionnaires digitally. Participants were contacted via email, with a personalized invitation explaining the study's purpose, the importance of their participation, and assurances of confidentiality. Follow-up reminders were sent to encourage responses. The respondents were mainly project managers and department managers (financial, sales, IT) (Table 3.1).

To gather rich, context-specific data, we developed tailored questionnaires for each partner group involved in the ADMIRAL marketplace. The questionnaire was organized into four sections. The introduction was the same for all companies, while the other sections were customized for each specific partner group. The first section that included six general questions aimed at assessing respondents' knowledge of or involvement in any marketplace, as well as their motivations and perceived risks associated with using, managing, or developing a marketplace solution. The second section encompassed three business-related questions, which

were based on three dimensions and the nine building blocks of the BMC. These questions examined topics such as: - How will purchasing logistics services or tools from the ADMIRAL marketplace change the value you offer to your customers? - How will the ADMIRAL platform affect the way you create value? - How will the ADMIRAL platform impact your revenue and cost models? Each question included at least four sub-questions to encourage more in-depth insights. The third section addressed concerns and risks and consisted of two questions, while the final section included three questions about the respondents' vision for the future.

All questions were open-ended to promote detailed, narrative responses. To ensure clarity, relevance, and logical flow, the draft questionnaires were reviewed by representatives from each stakeholder group. Revisions were made based on their feedback before finalizing the questionnaire. Enterprises were invited to complete the questionnaire between December 18, 2024, and February 15, 2025.

3.2.3. Sampling strategy

We used a purposive sampling strategy to select several representative companies from each of the three main partner groups active in the ADMIRAL project, (see detailed description of the project and the marketplace in the Section 4). This approach enhances the robustness, accuracy, and generalizability of our findings.

We selected six B2B case companies that are consortium partners of the ADMIRAL project to gather quality data (Table 3.1): Case company (CC) 1 is responsible for designing and managing a digital ecosystem based on an existing digital marketplace. Five companies (case companies 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6) are potential sellers or buyers of logistics services. Three companies provide parcel services, focusing on parcel transport and warehousing. One company specializes in less-than-truckload and full-truckload solutions, while another operates as a RO-RO operator and freight forwarder.

None of the six selected companies currently utilizes or manages a similar digital platform ecosystem, although most intend to adopt one in the future. Table 3.1 and Table 3.2 provide further details on the case companies.

Table 3.1 Descriptive overview of case companies

Case company	Platform role	Employees	Origin	Maturity	Position/department of the questionnaire respondent
1	PP	< 100	Finland	6-10	Vice president, Project manager
2	PS	100-500	Lithuania	≥ 11	Head of IT
3	PS/PB	500-1000	Finland	≥ 11	Controller, Financial department
4	PS	0	Croatia	6-10	CEO, Logistics specialist
5	PS	> 1000	Croatia	≥ 11	Project managers
6	PS	> 1000	Slovenia	≥ 11	Sales department, Parcel division, Innovations

Description: PP - Platform Provider, PS - Platform Seller, PB - Platform Buyer

Table 3.2 Description of case companies

Case company	Description
1	<p>Year established: 2008. Company headquarters: Turku, Finland. Core business: Port call planning and optimization tool, analytical AI/ML based services like maritime predictions. Local or international orientation: Internationally. Market share: 20 % in port call planning tools. Recent major changes/milestones:</p>
2	<p>Year established: 2009. Company headquarters: Vilnius, Lithuania. Core business: Transport services. Local or international orientation: Internationally. Market share: N/A.</p>
3	<p>Year established: 1848. Company headquarters: Kotka, Finland. Core business: Stevedoring, cargo handling, freight forwarding, freight transporting. Local or international orientation: Both. Market share: We are the largest operator. Other relevant details: Owned by the largest forest industry companies in Finland. Recent major changes/milestones: Russian transit traffic was important before the 2022.</p>
4	<p>Year established: 2016. Company headquarters: Velika Gorica, Croatia. Core business: Providing same-day delivery services through a crowdshipping platform. Local or international orientation: Local, Croatia. Recent major changes/milestones: The company continuously enhances its services to optimize last-mile delivery efficiency.</p>
5	<p>Year established: 1999. Company headquarters: Velika Gorica, Croatia. Core business: Postal services, parcel delivery, logistics services, financial services, digital and IT services. Local or international orientation: Both. Market share: 90 %. Recent major changes/milestones: The company strengthens its market position by expanding its logistics and parcel services, maintaining a strong customer focus. It is the leading logistics provider in the market and a pioneer in digital innovation.</p>
6	<p>Year established: 1994. Company headquarters: Maribor, Slovenia. Core business: Post services, parcels delivery, logistics services, IT services. Local or international orientation: Both. Market share: National (40%), international – N/A. Other relevant details: The biggest logistics provider in Slovenia with more than 450 contact points across Slovenia. Universal Service Provider in Slovenia.</p>

3.3. Data analysis

The responses from the questionnaires were analyzed using a hybrid coding approach that combines deductive and inductive methods. Guided by the BMC, we applied predefined codes corresponding to each of the nine building blocks. This ensured that our analysis remained anchored to established theoretical constructs. Following the initial coding, we conducted a comparative analysis by examining responses (1) within each actor group to uncover commonalities and intra-group differences and (2) cross-group patterns.

To contextualize our findings, we compared the results with existing research on B2B digital marketplaces and BM innovation in the logistics sector. This comparison (1) determined areas where our findings align with established literature, (2) highlight gaps and (3) uncover novel insights.

3.4. Synthesis and conclusion

Finally, we synthesized the insights derived from each actor group within the BMC framework, focusing on changes in nine building blocks, needs and requirements for BMC adaptation to better accommodate the dynamics of B2B digital logistics marketplaces.

4. Case context: ADMIRAL digital logistics marketplace ecosystem presentation

The ADMIRAL project aims to integrate maritime and other supply chain stakeholders in a unified digital platform ecosystem, helping users coordinate complex operations, share real-time information, and ultimately work more efficiently and sustainably (awake.ai, 2025). Primarily the marketplace platform aims to facilitate interaction between two different actors of the platform – sellers (producers) and buyers (consumers) (Figure 4.1 ADMIRAL digital marketplace ecosystem (Kääriäinen et al., 2024)). The sellers (e.g., Logistics Service Providers (LSPs) such as transport companies, freight forwarders and ports) operating on the platform offer their logistics services according to rules set by the platform operator (platform owner). The buyers (e.g., cargo owners) acquire these services from the sellers via the platform (Kääriäinen et al., 2024).

Figure 4.1 ADMIRAL digital marketplace ecosystem (Kääriäinen et al., 2024)

In addition to the aforementioned marketplace features (transaction platform), the platform aims to provide the ability for application developers and integrators to build and integrate external applications on top of the marketplace platform (innovation platform) to enrich the functionalities of the marketplace ecosystem. To facilitate this, developers offered a developer portal with documentation, examples, and a discussion forum. Therefore, the marketplace involves a rich set of stakeholders or actors that are expected to benefit from the platform (multisided platform).

The platform operator facilitates value creation among various actors by controlling access and contributions. In the ADMIRAL marketplace, the owner plays a vital role in developing technical solutions and defining conditions for activities and collaborations (Hein et al., 2020).

The ADMIRAL project’s platform, as noted by Madanaguli et al. (2023), transcends a basic industrial transaction system by integrating extensive client data to create, deliver, and capture value while connecting previously unlinked user groups. Client data is vital for its success.

The marketplace owner had already optimized port and ship operations, such as predicting Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and Estimated Time of Departure (ETD), and created a pilot marketplace that connected stakeholders through a single channel for physical and digital services. The ADMIRAL marketplace builds on these functionalities, reflecting the owner’s enhanced understanding of platform business (Figure 4.2 ADMIRAL marketplace will be built on top of the existing capability).

Figure 4.2 ADMIRAL marketplace will be built on top of the existing capability

The ADMIRAL marketplace serves multiple roles and offers a wide range of functionalities:

Roles

- Emission-aware multimodal logistics (seller and buyer):

Onboarding: Sellers and buyers register on the platform.

Sale setup: Sellers create listings for their logistics services, including low-emission options.

Matching/Purchasing: Buyers submit Requests for Quotations (RFQs) with specific requirements, such as low-emission services. Sellers respond to these RFQs, and the platform assists in finding suitable offers with emission predictions, leading to orders.

Fulfillment: The execution of logistics services is tracked, including location and emission predictions, while feedback is gathered from users.

Reporting: Customized reports on service fulfillment, including actual emissions, are provided.

- Application development and integration (developer and integrator):

Onboarding: Developers and integrators register on the platform.

Providing technical services: Developers create external applications to enhance the marketplace, adhering to guidelines from the platform owner and the business partner portal.

Integration: Existing IT systems, such as logistics management or Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, are connected to the ADMIRAL marketplace through Application programming interfaces (APIs) and the business partner portal.

Common Functionalities

- Listings: Services offered by sellers that can be traded on the marketplace.
- RFQ: Buyers issue RFQs, and sellers submit their quotes in response.
- Matching Engine: Helps buyers identify sellers who can meet their logistics needs.
- Emissions predictions and calculations: Tools for estimating and calculating emissions across multimodal transport chains.
- Other predictions: AI/ML-based estimations, such as Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and Estimated Time of Departure (ETD) for vessels.
- Route calculation and optimization: Offers analysis for multimodal transport chain routes.
- Developer and business partner portal: A web-based resource for knowledge sharing and guidance within the marketplace.
- APIs: Enable external companies to build and integrate solutions, thus reducing connection costs and promoting complementary innovations.
- Feedback – rating and recommendation system: Collects user feedback on service quality and marketplace content.
- Transport and shipment geographical location transparency: Allows sellers to share their location controlled by authorization, enabling only approved buyers to see it. This feature aids in route analysis and enhances emission calculations.

5. FINDINGS AND CONTEXTUALIZATION WITH PREVIOUS STUDIES

5.1. AS-IS vs. TO-BE BMCs: buyers and sellers

Five companies (potential buyers and sellers) provided both the AS-IS (current) and TO-BE (future) versions of their BMC (- Three companies (CCs 4-6) act as parcel carriers. - One company (CC 2) operates as a road transport company. - One company (CC 3) functions as a freight forwarder and as a RO-RO operator (Table 3.1 and Table 3.2).

Figure 5.1 Changes of BMCs from digital marketplace ecosystem use illustrates the various anticipated changes identified by potential buyer and sellers when adopting the ADMIRAL marketplace ecosystem. The changes most frequently mentioned are highlighted in grey.

Business Model Canvas		Changes from marketplace ecosystem use	Case studies 2,3-2x,8-10	Date: 23.05.2024	Version: final
Key Partners Platform sellers and buyers (3x) Marketplace ecosystem operator Eco-friendly transportation providers (2x) E-commerce companies Airline transport companies Railway operators Crowdsourcing providers Eco-friendly packaging suppliers	Key Activities CO ₂ emissions monitoring and reporting (5x) Development of low-emission services (2x) Route optimization (2x) Digital services on the marketplace Information sharing on arrivals and departures (2x)	Value Propositions Lower emissions (3x) More accurate emission information for customers (3x) Improved visibility and transparency (2x) Competitive pricing Regulatory compliance (2x) Leveraging data-driven insights and optimization (4x) Fast delivery Adjustable time slots	Customer Relationships Omnichannel support Feedback and reviews (2x) Community building (3x) Personalized assistance and recommendations (3x) Education Loyalty programs via e-shop Community building via e-shop	Customer Segments Companies with sustainability goals (5x) Renewable energy companies E-commerce companies Large corporations (2x) Commercial freight transporters (2x)	
Key Resources Marketplace infrastructure (3x) Telematics and route optimization software Carbon footprint calculator (2x) Sustainability certificates Freight forwarding software Comprehensive data (2x) Supply chain management expertise (2x) Regulatory knowledge (3x) Green delivery fleet Education and advocacy resources	Channels Marketplace ecosystem (5x) Industry events (2x) Public relations Paid advertising (2x) Social media marketing	Cost Structure Employee training on eco-driving Marketplace costs (fixed monthly fee / per-user fee) (5x) Marketing costs Investments in technology (4x)	Revenue Streams Automated CO ₂ calculation and reporting Consultations on eco-driving improvements and maintaining a low-emission company (2x) European Emissions Trading System (ETS) revenues Premium pricing for low-emission options/Profit margins on sustainable shipping costs (3x) Revenue streams from green services (e.g., green delivery and pickup)		

Figure 5.1 Changes of BMCs from digital marketplace ecosystem use

A comparative analysis of the AS-IS and TO-BE BMs revealed that companies anticipate changes in all nine blocks of the BMC as also noted by Veile et al. (2022). No building block remains unchanged. All six potential buyers and sellers of services within the marketplace ecosystem expect adjustments in key activities. Five companies foresee changes in key resources, channels, and revenue streams. Four companies reported expected changes in key partners and value proposition. Fewer changes (noted by three case companies) were identified in the area of customer segments and customer relationships. These findings align with Veile et al. (2022), which also observed that some blocks were more significantly affected than others, and—similarly to our case—customer segments and customer relationships were among the least frequently affected building blocks.

Most changes are related to the options offered by the marketplace ecosystem for calculating emissions. The Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) encourages firms to report their emissions. This presents an opportunity for case companies to partner with eco-friendly organizations, such as transport providers and packaging suppliers (n=4 case companies) and attract new customers who care about the environment (n=5 case companies).

For many case companies, automatic emission calculations represent a new avenue for offering and purchasing solutions (n= 5 case companies). The same applies for real data sharing which would improve visibility and transparency.

Companies on the other hand anticipate additional costs (fee) associated with using a marketplace (n=5 case companies), as well as the need to train personnel which would also cause additional costs. However, some believe that they will generate more revenue by offering and using more environmentally friendly solutions, such as better pricing for low-emission options and new value stream from offering green services.

Companies recognize that calculating emissions accurately based on real data necessitates robust data management and regulatory understanding, as noted by four case companies. Furthermore, two companies highlighted the significance of supply chain management expertise, particularly since the ADMIRAL marketplace provides multimodal transport options.

5.1.1. Value creation

Key partners

- **Collaboration with technology enterprises (n=5):** Most case companies believe that partnering with technology firms is essential for enhancing marketplace usage. One representative (CC6) explains, “*External expertise, such as consultant companies, is required to enhance our technological capabilities and ensure smooth integration with a digital marketplace*”. Notably, a study of Veile et al. (2022) identified data, technology, and IT solutions as key resources—underscoring the pivotal role of digital infrastructure. Interestingly, consultancy companies were also highlighted in their study. On the other hand, integrating competitors as partners was not mentioned by the case studies in our research, despite horizontal collaboration being an integral part of platform ecosystems.
- **Global reach (n=4):** Four companies plan to partner with international firms or subcontractors to expand their global presence and streamline cross-border logistics—a finding that aligns with a study of Bagnato and Giordino (2024), which investigated B2C digital marketplaces (as opposed to B2B). One company claimed that such expansion is not possible without leveraging a marketplace. This fact was also highlighted in a study of Ruggieri et al. (2018).
- **Green solutions (n=2):** Two companies intend to collaborate with eco-friendly carriers and producers of sustainable vehicles to provide more environmentally friendly transport options.

Key resources

- **Data collection and analysis (n=5):** Five companies confirm their plans to establish systems for data collection and analysis to enhance decision-making and foster innovation in digital marketplace operations. Notably, a study written by Bagnato and Giordino (2024)—despite its focus on B2C digital platforms—also revealed sweeping changes and innovations across various dimensions of business operations.
- **APIs and workflows (n=4):** Two companies specifically mention the necessity of APIs, while another two emphasize the importance of developing new workflows to handle customer queries and feedback in a digital context. Notably, a study of Veile et al. (2022) similarly identified data, technology, and IT solutions as key resources, underscoring the critical role of digital infrastructure in marketplace operations. Moreover, no company in this study mentioned predictive maintenance as a new offering from the platform, even though the platform provider has placed significant emphasis on it.

Key activities

- **Emission-focused operations (n=4):** Three case companies prioritize low-emission logistics to attract environmentally conscious consumers. Their plans include incorporating sustainable practices into daily operations, optimizing delivery routes to reduce emissions, and tracking emissions data.

5.1.2. Value offering

Value proposition

- **Cost savings** (n=4): Cost savings are identified as the primary benefit for both buyers and sellers, confirming the findings of Veile et al. (2022) and Bagnato and Giordino (2024).
- **Additional benefits** (n=2): Two companies highlight additional benefits such as improved tracking, lower emissions, and more flexible delivery options.
- **Specialized advantages** (n=1): One company emphasizes the benefits of predictive analytics, new transport modes, and a reduced manual workload within the marketplace.
- **Low-emissions differentiation** (n=3): Three case companies believe that prioritizing low-emission logistics will help differentiate their offerings.

Customer relationship

- **More frequent communication** (n=3): Sellers and buyers expect increased and more intensive engagement with customers through the marketplace which—a trend observed by all case companies in a study of Veile et al. (2022). However, while those companies reported that all communication would be automated, two companies in our case believe that personal support will still be essential.
- **Personalized support** (n=2): Despite the reliance on digital channels, two companies believe that personalized support will still be necessary.
- **Greater trust** (n=4): A seller representative (CC5) states, “*Increased transparency in operations will build trust and strengthen long-term customer relationships.*” Another representative (CC6) adds, “*Sustainable practices can foster long-term relationships with environmentally conscious customers*”. Similarly, Veile et al. (2022) also noted that higher transparency increases trust and contributes to lasting relationships while study of Korneeva et al. (2023) even claim that trust plays a major role in platform adoption.

Customer channels

- **Digital communication** (n=2): One representative (CC4) mentions, “*We will establish direct digital communication with our customers through the platform*”. Another (CC5) anticipates, “*We expect to focus more on stronger online engagement through the platform*”.

Customer segment

- **EU and green-conscious customers** (n=3): Some sellers and buyers consider that lower emissions and emissions calculation features will attract more European, environmentally conscious customers.

5.1.3. Value capture

Revenue streams

- **Pricing strategies** (n=2): Two companies indicate that while marketplace owners will determine pricing strategies, these must align with existing BMs. One company stresses

the need for simplicity for easy price comparisons, while the other seeks new pricing models to complement current practices.

- **Pay-per-use** (n=3): Three companies see potential in flexible, pay-per-use models for customers with occasional needs.
- **Value-added services** (n=2): Two companies are considering offering premium, fee-based services as an additional revenue stream.

Notably, the study of Veile et al. (2022) revealed that five case companies have also adopted premium revenue models.

Cost structure

- **Additional investments** (n=4): Four companies anticipate higher costs due to investments in technology infrastructure, sustainable fleets, APIs, and tools for emissions tracking and route optimization.
- **Potential savings** (n=3): Three companies believe that the platform could lead to reduced operational (transport) and marketing costs.

While the study of Veile et al. (2022) observed a decrease in fixed costs alongside an increase in licensing and subscription fees, our findings show that none of the companies reported rising human costs—aside from the need for training.

5.2. AS-IS vs. TO-BE BMCs: platform owner

The BMC of a platform owner indicates clear changes marked in red, which represent its evolution from a digital platform to a digital platform ecosystem capable of supporting multimodal transport emissions calculations (Figure 5.2 Changes in BMCs of digital marketplace ecosystem management).

The most substantial changes occur in the value proposition, key activities, customers and revenue streams blocks. These adjustments illustrate a strategic shift towards sustainability, multimodal logistics, technological advancement, and enhanced customer interactions.

Business Model Canvas		Transformations in marketplace ecosystem management	Platform provided	Date: 17.5.2024	Version: final
Key Partners Maritime ports Land hubs Freight forwarders Shipping agents Cargo owners & shippers SW developers SW integrators 3 rd party service providers 3 rd party data providers	Key Activities Complex SW development Customer research Marketing Onboarding assistance Developer assistance, developer portal Business partner material and business partner portal Discussion forum for both developers and business partners Key Resources Sellers & buyers Port services to be traded Cargo transport services to be traded Web marketplace Cloud infrastructure Support personnel 3 rd party service providers 3 rd party data providers	Value Propositions Sell faster & smarter Slash customer acquisition costs Gain EU-wide visibility instantly Elevate revenue with eco-friendly equipment Showcase reduced emissions transparently Boost revenue with multi-country, multimodal cargo routes Streamline purchases with efficient tools and transparent cargo insights Unlock new routes and services with reduced costs Get cloud-based logistics selling/purchasing and management tools (especially for SMEs) Buy faster & with more transparency Stay green with informed choices Easily switch to lower-emission logistics options Receive post-transport emissions calculations for comprehensive reporting at your fingertips Source all your multimodal, multi-country transport needs in one convenient platform. Rapid, intelligent buying handles more needs with fewer resources Track your cargo seamlessly and resolve issues faster Advanced RFQs, easily compare quote and their emissions	Customer Relationships Sellers & buyers must have a forum where they can provide feedback and ideas for improvement (business partner forum and discussion board). Participation to key association events to provide latest development and business opportunity news Newsletter Channels Maritime events Land side cargo transport events Maritime and land cargo associations Maritime and land cargo web sites and publications Maritime / land hub port events and publications	Customer Segments Port service sellers Port service buyers Port authorities Land hub service sellers Land hub service buyers Cargo transport sellers Cargo transport buyers Data providers (sellers) Integration developers	
Cost Structure Cloud infrastructure Marketplace headless SW engine provider Security & availability monitoring services	Routing engine(s), 3rd party emissions calculator(s) Development costs (maintaining SW) Developer & business partner community Discussion forum	Revenue Streams Monthly seller & buyer subscription Premium functionality features Premium vetting of organisations	Paid listings placement on catalogue and search results APIs usage fees Integration one-time fees Some sellers possibly in percentage commission mode		

Figure 5.2 Changes in BMCs of digital marketplace ecosystem management

The main reasons for transitioning to a platform ecosystem include the need for improved reporting on Scope 2 and Scope 3 emissions, the capability to support multimodal logistics chains, and the enhanced opportunities it offers to both developers and users of an online marketplace. Scalability is also a crucial factor. By adopting a platform approach, the platform provider expects to achieve: - Significant revenue growth. - A reduction in Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions. - Access to new customer segments. - Greater visibility and presence in international markets.

5.2.1. Value creation

Creating value relies on developing new capabilities in collaboration with ecosystem partners. This involves building an emission calculator, offering premium features for larger enterprises, providing mechanisms to build trust, and utilizing AI to improve various services. The provider recognizes that human and financial resources are significant risks in achieving these goals. Moreover, many companies in study of Ruggieri et al. (2018) identified human resources as a key asset. However, study of de Oliveira and Cortimiglia (2017) also points out that a critical risk in a digital ecosystem—overlooked in our study—is the clear identification of resources and competencies that each actor contributes to the co-creation process.

5.2.2. Value offering

The platform provider plans to deliver value in several ways:

- **Cost savings:** Increased competition among service providers in the marketplace will help reduce costs for end-users.
- **Expanded transport options:** This includes new possibilities such as rail transport, providing users with more sustainable choices.
- **Improved efficiency:** The platform will enable faster RFQs and reduce the time needed to find suitable logistics providers.
- **Real-time visibility:** Users will benefit from comprehensive tracking and situational awareness, which will assist in managing disruptions.
- **Broad range of logistics services & tools:** The provider will offer everything from specialized shipping options to advanced digital tools all in one place.
- **Ease of use:** The platform features a user-friendly interface and automated processes for a better user experience.

A representative (CC1) stated, *“The platform ecosystem will enhance situational awareness and provide tools to handle disruptions and other issues during the cargo fulfilment phase, which will save costs and keep end-customers satisfied”*. He also emphasized the platform's potential to *“combine buying and selling into a single ‘silo,’ reducing many inputs and outputs, as well as the time spent managing multiple communication channels”*.

The provider anticipates collaborating with new types of customers and partners in EU countries. However, this transition to platform ecosystem will require operational changes, such as automating billing cycles, updating terms of service, addressing privacy and legal aspects, and preparing for scenario detection. The provider believes that focusing on low-emission logistics, ensuring ease of use, and incorporating AI services will set them apart from competitors.

5.2.2.1. Value capture

The provider plans to generate revenue primarily through a subscription model. As a representative (CC1) explains, *“Our main revenue model is subscription-based, and we will*

introduce premium features about 6 to 12 months later. To attract a larger number of companies to the Marketplace, we will keep the subscription cost relatively low. Initially, we will likely offer three tiers: free, standard, and premium, which will be scaled based on the number of users and transactions allowed". The fair revenue distribution to all parties is an additional factor highlighted by de Oliveira and Cortimiglia (2017).

A platform provider acknowledges that maintaining and expanding the platform will incur additional costs, particularly for tools developed by external IT partners. However, they also anticipate benefiting from reduced marketing expenses and fixed costs once the marketplace gains traction. Low fixed costs were similarly noted by many companies building digital marketplaces in a study of Ruggieri et al. (2018).

5.3. Risks and challenges of using or managing digital platform ecosystem

A central challenge for the platform provider is ensuring frequent user engagement so that the marketplace becomes an active, "living" ecosystem, which was also confirmed by de Oliveira and Cortimiglia (2017). As one representative (CC1) explains, *"We're considering features like a news feed, light gamification, and tools that help boost sales or provide buyers with insights into supplier markets, activity levels, and pricing"*. To maintain this engagement, the provider must offer high-quality content and create a RFQ process that is easy, fast, and frustration-free. Another key concern is establishing and maintaining trust among users.

From the perspective of sellers and buyers, the primary risks revolve around commission and subscription fees. One seller's representative (CC2) highlights, *"Many marketplaces charge a commission on each transaction, which can cut into profit margins"*. Additionally, several sellers are worried about losing control over how their brands are presented on the marketplace, and others fear becoming overly dependent on the ADMIRAL platform.

Finally, both the platform provider and the users share concerns about data security and the potential misinterpretation of shared data. Ensuring robust data protection measures and clear guidelines for data usage will be critical to sustaining trust and encouraging ongoing participation. **These findings comprehensively address RQ4.**

6. CONCLUSIONS

Analysing the changes in BMs leads us to the following conclusions:

- Transitioning to an ecosystem model significantly enhances the platform's role in value creation. This transition includes the integration of multimodal transport chains, emissions calculations, various transaction types, and an expanded network of partners (Figure 0.1). Shifting from a basic marketplace to a marketplace ecosystem, as demonstrated by the digital platform developed in the ADMIRAL project, represents an innovation in BM. This response **addresses RQ1**. In contrast, buyers and sellers anticipate only minor changes, albeit across several building blocks of the BMC. Only one case company reported that they will need to implement new processes and workflows (Figure 0.1). The primary objectives of the case companies are to attract more customers, strengthen their market positions, and increase profits by incorporating new technology into their existing BMs, rather than developing entirely new activities or processes—which would necessitate employee training and new equipment development—a strategy that confirms researchers' statements on BM adaptation [Xie et al., 2022, Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010, Frishammar and Parida, 2019]. Therefore,

these changes are viewed as adaptations of BMs rather than full-scale innovations. These findings provide a direct **answer to RQ2**.

- Most changes in the BMs of sellers and buyers primarily focus on emission calculations rather than multimodal transport, revealing an unprecedented degree of BM transformation driven by the possibility of emissions assessment—a novel insight that has never been highlighted or investigated before. However, one logistics provider aims to partner with new air and rail operators, while two others seek to enhance their supply chain management expertise. In contrast, the platform provider is emphasizing multimodality as a way to differentiate its marketplace and attract a wider range of customers. Nevertheless, for many sellers and buyers, immediate concerns—such as costs, brand control, and regulatory compliance, particularly regarding emissions—may render multimodality more of a "nice-to-have" feature rather than an essential requirement.
- These findings **address RQ3** by analysing changes in BM elements across platform providers, sellers, and buyers, highlighting both shared and distinct aspects among these groups (Figure 0.1):

Value Offering: The platform provider, along with the majority of sellers and buyers, prioritize low-emission logistics, flexible delivery options, transparent operations, and expansion into new markets to attract more customers. They also plan to provide detailed emissions data to appeal to environmentally conscious clients. However, sellers and buyers place greater emphasis on more frequent and personalized communication with customers as a key driver of value—a point that is less significant for the platform provider.

Value Creation: The platform provider and sellers and buyers acknowledge the potential benefits of additional services, including AI, that are based on reliable data. This necessitates the establishment of robust systems for data collection and analysis. Five out of the six sellers and buyers share the need for high-quality data and collaboration with tech partners.

Value capture: All stakeholder groups—the platform provider, sellers, and buyers—anticipate higher costs for technology and training, but they also recognize opportunities for new revenue streams. Each group has its own pricing strategy to recover these investments. Nevertheless, most sellers and buyers intend to invest in new infrastructure to integrate with the marketplace, where cost savings, trust, and sustainability remain key priorities.

This study partially addresses the need for innovative frameworks and best practices to help create and manage new BMs within digital platforms and ecosystems, as called for by Martín-Peña et al. (2024). By highlighting potential changes, risks, and challenges that companies may encounter, it takes an important step toward bridging the gap between BM design and implementation. Additionally, it encourages others to differentiate their offerings within digital marketplaces. Furthermore, large-scale research is necessary to gather additional and more in-depth empirical data (including also complementors) and provide practical guidance, as well as the capabilities and resources required by platform managers and other stakeholders to build sustainable, data-driven, and profitable logistics ecosystems while effectively integrating platform channels.

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APPENDIX A

Figure 0.1 Overview of BM transformations and key changes in platform-based logistics ecosystems